

Spectrophotometric determination of the stability constant of iron Schiff base with cyanide ligand in aqueous micellar medium

Pradyut Sarma^{*a}, Prabin Kumar Boruah^b and Okhil Kumar Medhi^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Arya Vidyapeeth College, Guwahati-781 016, Assam, India

E-mail : gu_123456@yahoo.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Gauhati University, Guwahati-781 014, Assam, India

Manuscript received online 11 April 2013, revised 22 July 2013, accepted 29 December 2013

Abstract : Interaction of cyanide ion with ferric complexes provides a resemblance with cyanide antidote kit, useful for the treatment of cyanide toxicity. Iron Schiff base complex, [Fe(salen)]Cl has used in this work and its coordination with CN⁻ ion is studied in aqueous micellar medium. Aqueous micellar mediums are use to mimic the bio membrane condition and to portray the biological significance of the study. Critical micellar concentration of the micellar medium for the [Fe(salen)]Cl are investigated. The cmc values for the complex are within $7.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ to $7.21 \times 10^{-3} M$ concentration level. The stoichiometry of the [Fe(salen)CN] is studied by continuous variation method and mole ratio method. Benesi-Hildebrand method and Henry-Franck-Ostwald's method are used to calculated the stability constant of the [Fe(salen)CN] complex. The stability constant value is the maximum in neutral micellar medium.

Keywords : Cyanide antidote, aqueous micelle, CTAB, SDS, Triton X-100, stability constant.

Introduction

Complexes of Schiff bases are extensively studied due to synthetic flexibility, selectivity and sensitivity towards a variety of metal atom¹. The Schiff base complexes are found useful in catalysis, in medicine as antibiotics, as anti-inflammatory agent and in the industry as anticorrosion²⁻⁵. They are also found useful in biological activities like antimicrobial activities, antifungal activities, antiviral activities, synergistic action on insecticides, plant growth regulator, antitumor and cyclotoxic activities; such complexes are also applicable in industrial field as anti-corrosion, as inhibitor of emulsion polymerization etc. Cyanide occurs in seeds of fruits such as apricot, cherries, peaches and plums. Cyanide exerts its toxic action by inhibiting oxidative phosphorylation. Poisons can act in a variety of ways but the most deadly of them is by inhibiting enzymes. They may do this by tying up an enzyme in the form of stable complex or by denaturing it or by blocking its formation from the apoenzyme. Cyanide acts almost instantly and only a small amount is needed for lethal dose. Cyanokit is the brand name of cyanide antidote kit which uses hydroxycobalamin to react with cyanide to form cyanocobalamin, which can be

eliminated by kidneys. The goal of this antidote is to generate a large pool of ferric iron to compete with cytochrome a₃ for cyanide. Studied has revealed^{4,5} that Fe^{III} complexes can form effective bonding with strong field ligand like CN⁻, CO etc. Fe³⁺ ion co-ordinates with CN⁻ ligand with high value of stability constants due to the π acceptor behaviour of CN⁻. These co-ordinations produce $d\pi-\pi^*$ transition of electrons from filled *d* orbital of metal to empty π^* orbital of ligand. Therefore Fe-Schiff base complex provides a good probability to coordinate with cyanide ligand. Hence stable [Fe(salen)(CN)] complex can be presented as a new route to provide biological cyanide antidote tool. To correlate this project with biological membrane system aqueous micelles are utilized as the reaction medium. Cationic (CTAB), anionic (SDS) and neutral micelle (Triton X-100) are used in this experiments. The hydrophobic and hydrophilic environments of the micellar medium are expected to provide proper biomimetic conditions to this work⁶⁻⁹. In this work we have emphasized on the evaluation of composition of [Fe(salen)(CN)] complex as well as corresponding stability constant values.

Results and discussion

[Fe(salen)]Cl is sparingly soluble in water but more soluble in aqueous micellar medium above the cmc concentration. The electronic spectra of [Fe(salen)]⁺ complex in CTAB micelles produce λ_{\max} at 320 nm in acidic medium (pH \approx 4.5), whereas at high pH (pH \approx 7.5) the λ_{\max} undergoes a red shift to 398.6 nm. As the pH of the solution gradually increases (4.5–7.5), the intensity of the band at 320 nm diminished slowly with simultaneously growth of a new band at 398.6 nm¹⁰. The variation of the absorbance of [Fe(salen)]⁺ are examined against a particular wavelength viz. λ_{\max} 398.6 nm with increasing concentration of surfactant (Table 1) (Fig. 1). In case of all the three surfactants, the complex exhibits an identical change in absorbance with rise in concentration of surfactants^{11(a)}. This analysis leads to the calculation of cmc values of CTAB, SDS and Triton X-100 micelles as given below. To obtained cmc spectrophotometrically, stock solution of the ferric complex of 5.0×10^{-5} M is prepared. Solutions of the surfactants are then prepared using the ferric complex solution as solvent. Using the method of Corrin and Harkins^{11(b)} the stock ferric complex solution is then titrated into 25 mL of the surfactant

Table 1. Electronic spectral data of [Fe(salen)]Cl complex in aqueous surfactant micelles at pH 7.5

Complex	λ_{\max} (nm)			pH
	CTAB	SDS	Triton X-100	
[Fe(salen)]Cl	322, 398.6	320, 427.2	328, 443.2	7.5

Fig. 1. Change in absorbance of [Fe(salen)]⁺ with the increase in surfactant concentration. ([Fe(salen)]⁺ = 3×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, pH 7).

ferric complex solution and the absorbance measured at 398.6 nm at various dilutions of the surfactants. This allowed the determination of the absorbance of a constant concentration of ferric complex solution as a function of the surfactant concentration (Fig. 1). Below the cmc, the ferric complex sparingly dissolves in the aqueous surfactant solution and the absorbance of the solution remains low. At the cmc, a sudden rise in the solutions absorbance is observed, as the complex is encapsulated in micelles and dissolves in solution. Above the cmc, the absorbance of the solution increases linearly with increasing concentrations. This is an indication of micellization of the complex under investigation^{10–12}. Cmc values of the surfactants as calculated by above method are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Critical micellar concentration (cmc) values of the surfactants in presence of [Fe(salen)]⁺

Complex	Surfactant	cmc values
[Fe(salen)]Cl	CTAB	$(2.10\text{--}4.31) \times 10^{-3}$ M
	SDS	$(3.12\text{--}7.21) \times 10^{-3}$ M
	Triton X-100	$(6.10\text{--}7.53) \times 10^{-4}$ M

However it is important to note that the exact value of cmc depends on various factors, such as ionic strength, temperature and the nature of the solute. It is noteworthy to mention that in this work, all experiments are carried out by maintaining the critical micellar concentration of the micelle solution; because it would reduce the chances of any minor fluctuation of absorbance values due to any slight variation of concentration of micellar medium.

Coordination of π -acceptor ligand CN⁻ with [Fe(salen)]⁺ is well characterized (at pH 7.5) by a newly formed band at 714 nm in CTAB micelle. This band position is highly significant and gives an indication of the formation of new [Fe(salen)(CN)] adduct (Fig. 2). The existence of isosbestic points is indications about the number of states occur in the system and a further proof of the new complex formation. The characteristic λ_{\max} value of the formation of [Fe(salen)(CN)] in SDS and Triton X-100 micelle are also recorded at 690 nm and 704 nm respectively.

The stoichiometry of the complex in all micellar medium are determined by both continuous variation method and mole ratio method^{13–15}. Absorbance measurements

Fig. 2. Electronic spectral changes observed upon gradual addition of CN^- to $3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$ complex ion in CTAB micelle.

are made at constant pH value 7.5. The ionic strength of the ferric complex solution is bringing up to a constant value of 0.1 mol dm^{-3} by means of NaNO_3 solution (1 mol dm^{-3}). For the continuous variation method, $4.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ solution of ferric complex and equimolar cyanide solution are used and a series of mixtures containing $y \text{ mL}$ of metal ion solution and $(25 - y) \text{ mL}$ of the ligand solution are made upto 25 mL standard solution mixture. All the measurements are made at 714 nm . The changes in absorbance are plotted against the mole fraction of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$ solution (Fig. 3). The curve displayed a

Fig. 3. Determination of stoichiometry of the $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})\text{CN}]$ complex by Job's method of continuous variation : ($C_M = C_L = 4.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH 7.5).

maximum at a mole fraction $\lambda [\text{Fe}(\text{Salen})]^- = 0.5$ which indicates the formation of 1 : 1 $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})(\text{CN})]$ complex.

According to the discussion present in the literature¹⁶, a little deviation observed between the experimental and theoretical value is predictable, which is attribute to the stability of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})(\text{CN})]$ adduct. This Job's curve does not have a sharp maximum, which point out to the composition of the complex. When complex formation is simultaneously accompanied by considerable dissociation or when several complexes are formed having similar stability, then such shape of curve is characteristics¹⁷.

Line **a** (in Fig. 3) represents extrapolation of the linear section of curve **b**. The coordination of the break point is obtained by intersecting the extrapolated line equation and the break points are A_a (i.e. Absorbance) = 0.442 and χ_L (i.e. mole fraction) = 0.50. This intersection point represents the situation in which dissociation of the complex is negligible. The normal maximum absorbance with coordination of $A_b = 0.354$ and $\chi_L = 0.50$, is considered as the maximum point of curve of **b**. Nevertheless, A_a and A_b values are obtained at an equal mole fraction values of CN^- ligand and hence the mole fraction corresponding to A_a is used in equation of curve **b** and the resulted absorbance is considered as A_b value. The complex formation constant K is then calculated from the following equation (eq. 1),

$$K = \frac{A_b/A_a}{C_M (1 - A_b/A_a)^2} \quad (1)$$

where, C_M is the initial analytical concentration of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$ at the maximum point of A_a and A_b . The K values are calculated in the three different micellar mediums and the values are reported in Table 3. K value is calculated as no significant difference is observed using the F and t -test at 95% confidence level between the two

Table 3. Stability constant values calculated by Job's method, Benesi-Hilderbrand and Henry-Franck-Ostwald methods in the three different micellar medium

Complex	Medium	Job's Method	Benesi-Hildebrand method	Henry-Franck-Ostwald's method
		$K = \frac{A_b/A_a}{C_M(1 - A_b/A_a)^2}$		
$[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})(\text{CN})]$	CTAB	6.12×10^3	6.54×10^3	6.83×10^3
	SDS	6.19×10^3	6.61×10^3	6.93×10^3
	Triton X-100	6.35×10^3	6.92×10^3	7.11×10^3

values obtained from the above techniques¹⁷.

The composition of the complex is also determined by applying the mole ratio method. A series of solutions are prepared with a constant concentration of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$ ($3.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and a variable concentration of CN^- (2.5×10^{-4} to $6.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). These variations are plotted as absorption vs $[\text{CN}^-]/[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]$ in Fig. 4. Fig. 4 indicates the ligand/metal ratio in the complex as 1 : 1, which agrees with result obtained by the Job's method. After 1 : 1 ratio, a steady increase of the absorbance of the complex with increasing ligand concentration indicated that a complex of lower stability has formed¹⁷. The experiment has carried out in all the three micellar medium and exhibit similar sort of output.

Fig. 4. Determination of the stoichiometry of the $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})\text{CN}]$ complex by the mole ratio method : ($C_M = 3.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $C_L = 2.5 \times 10^{-4}$ to $6.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH 7.5).

The modified procedure of Benesi-Hildebrand equation¹⁴ is utilized to calculate stability constant (K) for $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})(\text{CN})]$. 1 : 1 complex formation between $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$ and CN^- in micellar medium can be represented by the following equation (eq. 2).

$$K = \frac{[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})\text{CN}]}{[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})\text{CN}^-]}$$

Benesi-Hildebrand equation,

$$\frac{[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]}{\Delta Abs} = \left(\frac{1}{[\text{CN}]} \right) \left(\frac{1}{K\varepsilon} \right) + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \quad (2)$$

where, ΔAbs is the change in absorbance upon addition of CN^- , while $[\text{CN}^-]$ is the concentration of ligand CN^- .

The value of K is determined from the slope and the

intercept obtained from a linear regression analysis of the

“double reciprocal linear plot” of $\frac{[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]}{\Delta Abs}$ vs $\frac{1}{[\text{CN}^-]}$.

Fig. 5 shows the Benesi-Hildebrand plot of stability constant data of interaction of CN^- with $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$ complex ion in CTAB micelle. The magnitude of the formation constant is a measurement of stability constant of a coordination complex in a thermodynamic sense¹⁸⁻²⁰.

Fig. 5. Determination of the stoichiometry and relative stability constant of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})\text{CN}]$ in CTAB micelle by Benesi-Hildebrand method : ($C_M = 3.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $C_L = 2.5 \times 10^{-4}$ to $6.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH 7.5).

Henry-Franck-Ostwald's method is also equally useful in calculating the stability constant for complexes with metal ligand ratio 1 : 1¹⁸. A series of solution has prepared by mixing variable concentration of NaCN (1.5×10^{-4} – $4.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) with constant concentration of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})\text{Cl}]$ ($4.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and their corresponding absorbances have recorded. Henry-Franck-Ostwald's method utilizes the following equation (eq. 3),

$$\frac{C_M C_L}{A} = \frac{1}{\varepsilon} (C_M + C_L) + \frac{1}{\varepsilon K} \quad (3)$$

A straight line has obtained for $C_L C_M/A$ as a function of $C_L + C_M$ (Fig. 6) from eq. (3). Fig. 6 shows the calculation of stability constant for the complex in the three micellar medium. Here C_M and C_L account for the concentration of metal complex (i.e. $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$ ion) and concentration of ligand ion (i.e. $[\text{CN}^-]$). ε (molar absorptivity) can be determine from the slope of the straight line and K can be determine from the intercept²¹⁻²⁴. The straight line confirm the previous conclusion of 1 : 1 complex composition and stability constants are calculated as 6.83×10^3 (in CTAB micelle), 6.93×10^3 (in

Fig. 6. Determination of the stoichiometry and relative stability constant of [Fe(salen)CN] in the three different micellar mediums by Henry-Franck-Ostwald's method : ($C_M = 3.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $C_L = 2.5 \times 10^{-4}$ to $6.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH 7.5).

SDS micelle) and 7.11×10^3 (in Triton X-100 micelle) (Table 3).

The stability constant values for the [Fe(salen)(CN)] coordination as measured by the different procedures are in fair agreement.

Stability constant value of [Fe(salen)(CN)] complex is slightly higher in neutral surfactant. This is definitely due to the favourable environment provided by the surfactant medium to the newly formed ferric complex. The neutral head groups of the micelle don't produce any electrostatic repulsion with [Fe(salen)(CN)] species. This may create a positive entropy change and account for higher stability constant value of the concern complex encapsulated in the micelle. However, in CTAB and SDS micelle stability constant values are lowered and both the micelles produce almost similar range of stability constant values. The overall high stability of Fe^{3+} complex may be explained on the basis of the differences in the charge of the metal ions, the high positive charge on the iron permits a closer approach of the ligand and the better electrostatic attraction. This resulted in the formation of more stable complexes with ligands. However, it is a common knowledge that M^{3+} ions form stronger conformation than M^{2+} and M^{+} . The working have emphasized on the basicity of the ligand as one of the factors governing the stability of complexes.

Conclusion

In this work, stability constant of the [Fe(salen)]⁺ complex with π -acceptor ligand has been determined by

using spectrochemical procedure. The spectrophotometric procedure is critically evaluated with particular regard to linearity and range of calibration graph, precision, and limit of detection and effect of interfering ions¹³. The formation constant values are also systematized in micelle medium to mimic the biological interfaces and medium provide slight interference in the result. The aim of the cyanide antidote is to generate a large excess of Fe^{3+} to complete with cytochrome a_3 for cyanide. The formation constant of [Fe(salen)CN] may open up a possibility to use the ferric complex as a part of cyanide antidote. It may be a better option to accelerate the detoxification due to cyanide accumulation.

Experimental

Materials :

Salicylaldehyde, ethylenediamine are purchased from Merck chemicals. We use cationic (CTAB), anionic (SDS) and neutral micelles (Triton X-100) in our experiments and they are all purchased from Sigma Chemicals Co., USA and have used without further purifications. NaCN is purchased from Aldrich Chem.

Methods :

Synthesis of ligand, 1,2-bis(2-hydroxybenzylidene-amino)ethane or salenH₂ :

The Schiff base ligand (salen) has synthesized according to the published procedures^{25,26}. Salen is Schiff base ligand which is synthesized by condensation of ethylenediamine with salicylaldehyde. Salen ligand provides the right coordination geometry of the synthetic models for the active sites of the non-heme iron enzymes. The phenolate moieties of the Schiff base can mimic the two tyrosine (Tyr) coordination, while the imine functionalities and co-ordinated imidazoles enzyme provide some correspondence to the histidine (His) coordination in a nonheme iron enzyme. The composition of the Schiff base ligand and complex is confirmed by electronic spectra, IR spectra and elemental analysis. The nature of the charge transfer bands of the Fe^{III} Schiff base complexes are well documented by Lever²⁵ and Que (Jr.)²⁶⁻³⁰. For the Fe^{III} salen complex the band observed 420–530 nm are assigned to P_π (phenolate) – d_π (Fe^{3+}) transition^{29,30}. UV-Visible spectra are recorded in a Hitachi U-3210 model as well as in Perkin-Elmer Lambda 40 UV/Vis spectrometer. The pH measurements are done by Elico made model No. L1-

10 pH meter. Infra-red spectra are recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum RX-I FT-IR System spectrophotometer. Elemental analysis is recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Series II CHN analyzer 2400.

References

1. T. Dhanalakshmi, M. Bhuvaneshwari and M. Palaniandavar, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2006, **100**, 1527.
2. R. Mayilmurugan, E. Suresh and M. Palaniandavar, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2007, **46**, 6038.
3. D. H. Ohlendorf, A. M. Orville and J. D. Lipscomb, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1994, **244**, 586.
4. A. D. Allian, Y. Z. Wang, M. Saeys, G. M. Kuramshina and M. Garland, *Vibrational Spectroscopy*, 2006, **41**, 101.
5. W. F. Liaw, J. H. Lee, H. B. Gau, C. H. Chen, S. J. Jung, C. H. Hung, W. Y. Chen, C. H. Hu and G. H. Lee, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 1680.
6. D. K. Das, C. Bhattaray and O. K. Medhi, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1997, 4713.
7. D. K. Das and O. K. Medhi, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1998, 1693.
8. S. S. S. Saini, O. K. Medhi and A. L. Verma, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2000, **322**, 293.
9. D. K. Das and O. K. Medhi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2005, **44**, 2228.
10. P. Sarma, P. K. Boruah, S. K. Baruah and O. K. Medhi, *Int. J. Chem. Res.*, 2011, **2**, 135.
11. (a) P. Sarma, P. K. Baruah and O. K. Medhi, *J. Surface Sci. Technol.*, 2011, **27**, 135; (b) M. L. Corrin and W. D. Harkins, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 676.
12. P. Sarma and O. K. Medhi, *Curr. Res. Chem.*, 2011, **3**, 87.
13. H. A. Benesi and J. H. Hildebrand, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2703.
14. M. Lamsa and T. Kuokkanen, *J. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1996, **9**, 21.
15. N. J. Rose and R. S. Drago, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 6138.
16. A. Saha, S. K. Nayak, S. Chattopadhyay and A. K. Mukherjee, *J. Phy. Chem. (A)*, 2004, **108**, 8223.
17. M. V. Obradovic, S. S. Mitic, S. B. Tosic and A. N. Pavlovic, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **70**, 651.
18. H. S. Franck and R. L. Ostwald, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 1321.
19. L. V. Mulaudzi, J. F. Staden and R. I. van. Stefan, *Analytical Chemica Acta*, 2002, **35**, 467.
20. M. Kass and A. Ivaska, *Talanta*, 2002, **58**, 1131.
21. M. Baranska, E. G. Kontecka, H. Kozlowski and L. W. Proniewicz, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2002, **92**, 112.
22. M. Baranska, W. Lasocha, H. Kozlowski and L. M. Proniewicz, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2004, **98**, 991001.
23. A. Domenech, A. Garcca-Espana, P. Pilar Navarro and F. Reviriego, *Talanta*, 2000, **51**, 625.
24. S. L. Wu and W. D. Horrocks (Jr.), *Anal. Chem.*, 1996, **68**, 394.
25. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.
26. R. B. Lauffer, R. H. II Heistand and L. Que (Jr.), *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 3947.
27. M. Costas, M. P. Mehn, M. P. Jensen and L. Que (Jr.), *Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **104**, 939.
28. M. Higuchi, Y. Hitomi, H. Minami, T. Tanaka and T. Funabiki, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2005, **44**, 8810.
29. L. Que (Jr.) and M. Reynolds, *Met. Ions Biol. Syst.*, 2000, **37**, 505.
30. L. Que (Jr.), C. K. Richard and S. W. Lloyd, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **109**, 5373.